

PATRIOTISM IS THE BASIS OF OUR NATIONAL IDEOLOGY

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Abstract: The formation of patriotism in the minds of young people and their education in the spirit of devotion to universal values is an important task today, and in our opinion, instilling national-independence ideas into the minds of the military is an urgent issue of today. Because the military guards the borders of our country, they are literally shields of the country. This article talks about the rich historical legacy of our nation in educating patriotic people.

Keywords: people, homeland, patriotic feeling, worldview, historical heritage.

Patriotism is respect and loyalty to our dear and beautiful country. The sense of homeland is the desire to study the golden heritage of our people living in the land of Turan, Movarunnahr, Turkestan and now Uzbekistan, and its history. "Watan" is an Arabic word meaning motherland. Ibn Khaldun, the great scholar of the East, said: "Motherland is a man's native land, the hearth of his love since childhood," Abdullah Awlani also said, "The city and country where a person was born and raised is called his Motherland". Everyone loves the husband he was born and grew up with more than his life. Even animals have this feeling of Motherland. "If an animal loses its homeland, it will not live as comfortably as it did in its land, its life

will be miserable, and the love of its homeland will always be in the corner of its tongue.”

The historical heritage of our people is of great importance in educating patriotic people. For this reason, preserving, studying and leaving the historical heritage to future generations has become one of the priorities of our state's policy. As a person grows up, his understanding of the Motherland also expands. Every person born and raised in our country means the Republic of Uzbekistan, not his home, village or city, when he says “Motherland”. This is the expression of the feeling of the Motherland, patriotism in the hearts of our people. In our holy religion, standing in the ranks of the military for the protection of one's mother, family, and homeland is considered one of the most meritorious actions. In the hadiths, it is said, “Standing against the enemy for one day and night is better than fasting for a month and praying at night” (narration of Imam Muslim).

In our nation, proverbs such as “Be a king in another country, be a poor man in your own country”, “Your country is peaceful - you are peaceful”, “Your motherland is your golden cradle”, “A person without a country is a nightingale without a tune” are dedicated to valuing the country. In the ancient thousand-year history of our homeland, the great courage of the brave children who defended our country from the invaders was written in golden letters in the history of our nation. Their exemplary life and activities have been an example and example for our people for centuries. They gave their lives for the Motherland without hesitation, including Tomaris, Shiroq, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Najmuddin Kubro, Mahmud Torabi, Amir Temur, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, representatives of modernism, representatives of national independence movements, including Madaminbek. Here it is appropriate to say that in the patriotic courage of our great-grandfathers, bravery and tenacity in the literal sense of the highest form of patriotism were realized. The reason is that they showed that the land is sacred in front of the enemy, they did not follow the path of compromise,

thinking about their own well-being. Most of them are statesmen who left an indelible mark not only in our national history but also in world history. Most of them are statesmen who left an indelible mark not only in our national history but also in world history. In the following years, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev gave the names of our great national commanders to advanced military units, instructed the creation of scientific researches, artistic works, and films about our great commander-in-chief, and became an important event in the scientific study of our national military heritage. The great historian, Shihobiddin Muhammad al-Nasawi, very rightly said, "Is there anything more important and nobler in the world than immortalizing the events of the past by writing them, drawing conclusions from the experiences of our ancestors, and making the generations interested in the heritage of the Prophet!"

Our great scholars who came out of our country set personal examples in educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland and expressing love for their country. Our great scholars have set personal examples in educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland, expressing love for their country, and associated their nickname with the country where the navel blood was shed. For example, patriotic scholars such as Imam al-Bukhari, Imam al-Tirmizi, Muhammad ibn Musa Khorezmi, Ahmad Farghani, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, Mahmud az-Zamakhshari, Burhoniddin Marginani, Abdurazzaq Samarkandi, Qaffol Shoshi made the name of the Motherland famous in the world. is an example.

Alikhontora Soguni writes in the work "The Sorrow of Turkistan": "There are four things that are dearest to a person. Those who do not have these four things are deprived of human dignity:

- the first of them is that every person has his own free will. What is the difference between people who do not have a will and do not have a will from an animal?

- the second - the world of wealth earned through legal professions, the fruit of his labor is the rightful property of the earner.

- the third is the real mother of every nation, she is the motherland of the nation, born and raised, inherited from her forefathers. Leaving the Motherland in the hands of others is an unforgivable crime committed by the descendants of the Motherland, but also a betrayal of human rights.

- the fourth is the sacred religions of the people of every country that have been preserved for centuries”.

The scientist's opinion that “Life and freedom deserve only the person who fights for them every day” has not lost its relevance. “If we want to know a person's loyalty, it can be seen from his concern for the Motherland,” his opinion is extremely reasonable.

As a conclusion, as Patriotism forms the basis of our national ideology, it was considered necessary to put forward the following points regarding its formation:

- It would be correct to understand the meaning of patriotism as patriotism;
- The concept of “loyalty to the motherland” is equal to everyone. In particular, loving the Motherland and protecting it is a sacred duty not only of military personnel, but also of every citizen. That is, love for the country, contributing to its prosperity and development belongs to representatives of all spheres of society;

- studying our spirituality, scientific, cultural, military heritage and values, presenting them to the future generation;

- to continue the work of great ancestors, to be their worthy successor.

The development of the country is one of the highest concepts of our national idea, and it depends on the education and maturity of our citizens. Each of our compatriots, regardless of the field in which he serves, should fully understand this fact, feel responsible for his spiritual maturity, live in harmony with the interests of

this country and this people, and educate the growing young generation as a perfect person.

That's why President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "Patriotism is the moral basis of the life of every state and it is the most important mobilizing force for the comprehensive development of the society," and highly evaluated this process.

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